

IMPACT RESPONSE OF CARBON FIBRE ROD, WITH AND WITHOUT A TENSIONED KEVLAR OVERWIND

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SUMMARY: Sensitivity to impact plays a major role in limiting the design strains available in carbon fibre composite laminates and structures. Relatively low energy impacts can give rise to splitting in unidirectional composites, and delamination in multi-axial laminates, due to transverse and through thickness tensile stresses induced by the impact. This damage can then propagate under compressive loading leading to a great reduction in compressive strength. If the components could have imposed on them a transverse compressive pre-stress this would offset the effects of impact and lead to structures that are less sensitive to impact. The work reported here covers the imposition of such a pre-stress by overwinding structural elements with aramid fibre under considerable tension. The level of prestress in overwound rods has been investigated. Rod specimens have been impacted and tested after impact; a very substantial increase in compressive strength after impact has been observed.

KEYWORDS: Impact, compressive strength after impact, aramid fibres, overwinding.

INTRODUCTION

The influence of impact loadings on carbon fibre composites has been widely studied, refs 1-3. The primary effects of low energy impact are longitudinal splitting in unidirectional laminates and delamination in multi-directional laminates. At higher energies fibre failure can be seen in addition to the matrix dominated failure modes. The damage state generated by the impact will propagate when a compressive stress is applied to the laminate or structure, resulting in premature failure and limiting the design strain allowables to much lower values than could be attained in the absence of impact damage. The damage that occurs during the impact event is triggered by transverse and through-thickness tensile stresses. Typical laminates might be able to tolerate stresses in these modes of a few tens of MPa before some damage was generated. One approach to the protection of composite structures against the effects of impact is therefore to prevent the emergence of tensile stresses. In principle this can be achieved by the establishment of a compressive pre-stress, which must be overcome before any damage can be either initiated or propagated. For the case of components of circular cross-section this can be achieved by winding aramid fibres under high tension around the components. The work reported here was carried out in order to verify that this approach is valid and to determine the level of protection against the deleterious effects of impact that can be obtained by the imposition of a compressive transverse pre-stress.

APPLICATION OF A TENSIONED OVERWIND

Methodology/equipment

Unidirectional composite rods were manufactured by assembling an array of preimpregnated single IM7 tows (Graphlite rods, ref. 4) in a tool and introducing additional matrix resin by RTM to give a solid rod of CFRP of 12.36mm and a total fibre volume fraction of 47%. Neither the matrix in the rods themselves, nor the additional matrix (MY750/HY915) was a toughened system.

The winding was carried out using a dead-weight tensioning system. A lathe was used for rotation and translation and the aramid fibre was applied with the minimum number of changes of direction to minimise damage to the fibres. The rod samples were mounted in one of the end fittings to be used for impact and compression testing and the other end was supported in a lightweight cup for overwinding.

Winding patterns employed

A 'standard' winding pattern of 7 layers of 4560 denier kevlar 49 fibre at a pitch of 2mm and a tension of 157N was employed for most rod samples. This gave a total aramid fibre thickness of 1.55mm at an average volume fraction of 78% and an initial tension in the fibre of 449MPa.

In addition to this 'standard' pattern windings were carried out at:

7 layers at 80.4N; 7 layers at 16.7N, 3 layers at 157N and 3 layers at 16.7N, all at a pitch of 2mm.

INVESTIGATION OF THE LEVEL OF PRESTRESS.

As successive layers of aramid fibres are laid down under tension each new layer will tend to compact the layers that have been previously wound. This effect will tend to reduce the additional pressure that each layer of aramid fibre can achieve. To understand the overwinding process the compressibility of the aramid fibres must be known.

Measurement of the compressibility of aramid fibres under transverse compaction

The compressibility was measured by winding a known number of aramid tows around a flat GRP former, which was a close fit in the measurement jig to prevent lateral spreading of the tows. The jig is shown in fig 1.

The distance between the two plattens was measured using a video extensometer, ref. 6. and the data obtained was used to generate volume fraction/reduction in thickness versus applied pressure curves. A figure for the effective packing stiffness was then extracted from the reduction in thickness versus pressure curve for use in modelling the overwinding process. This procedure was carried out for both unimpregnated strands and for strands lightly impregnated with polyurethane rubber (PU) and cured prior to winding. The intent of the impregnation was to increase the packing stiffness whilst not losing ease of handling. Fig 2 shows volume fraction versus pressure curves for both unimpregnated and impregnated strands.

Fig 1. Jig for measuring compaction properties of aramid fibres.

Fig 2. Volume fraction versus compaction pressure curves for dry and impregnated tows

Fig 2. shows that the dry aramid tows compacted to about 83% Vf, whereas the partial impregnation limited the rubberised tows to 68% Vf. If the graphs are drawn in terms of reduction in thickness versus compaction pressure then an effective compaction stiffness for the straight line portion of the curves can be extracted as the pressure for a nominal 100% compaction. This figure works out at 370MPa for the dry aramid yarns and 1080MPa for the yarns with partial PU impregnation.

The dry aramid tows were impregnated with epoxy resin, sectioned and polished to detect any damage done by the high consolidation pressures. The majority of fibres can be seen to have maintained their circular cross-section, however a minority of fibres have been distorted by the pressure, demonstrating that the pressure is not carried uniformly by all of the fibres in the sample.

Instrumented overwinding of rods.

A strain gauge was applied to the samples in the hoop direction and the samples were then overwound with a single tow of 4560denier kevlar 49 carrying a tension of 157N (446MPa stress). The hoop strain was monitored after each layer was applied and the build-up of compressive strain is shown in fig 3.

Fig 3. Induced hoop strain in rod vs number of layers of overwind at 16kg tension

The aramid fibre volume fraction of a rod overwound with seven layers of tensioned aramid fibre was measured at an average of 78%, this equates to a radial compressive stress of about 33MPa, from fig 2. For composites manufactured by embedding the Graphlite rods in an epoxy matrix the transverse modulus has been measured at Bristol University and found to be 8.3GPa. The hoop strain was measured at 0.24%. The radial stress arising from this strain can be estimated by

$$\sigma_r = \epsilon_h * E_t / (1 - \nu)$$

Where: σ_r = radial stress; ϵ_h = hoop strain; E_t = transverse modulus & ν = Poisson's ratio

On this basis the radial compressive stress is estimated to be about 36MPa for a Poisson's ratio of 0.45, which is in reasonable agreement with the value estimated from the volume fraction in the aramid overwind layer.

A preliminary FEA analysis of the overwinding of tubular structures indicates that the lay-up of the tubes has an important role to play in the development of the imposed stress state. For pure UD tubes a small amount of overwinding can produce substantial hoop compressive stresses, but gives rise to low values of radial prestress. For cross-plyed tubes or tubes containing hoop-wound fibres on the inner surface of the tube larger levels of radial prestress can be generated. From this work it is anticipated that substantial improvements in the impact resistance should also be available for at least some variants of composite tube. To date no experimental results on modifications to impact performance in overwound tubular specimens have been obtained.

IMPACT TESTING

Overwound CFRP rods

The overwound CFRP elements were bonded into substantial steel end fittings for impact and compression testing, as shown in fig 4. The assembled samples were then clamped as rigidly as possible to the heavy cast iron bed of the impact rig to minimise any movement. The impact rig consisted of a guided square section steel weight carrying a 10mm diameter

hardened steel rod indenter set to impact with its long axis perpendicular to that of the specimen.

Impact testing was first carried out on unprotected rods to establish suitable test regimes for the impacting of the protected rods. Impact tests were carried out at 2, 5, 10 & 40J. At 2J there was no clear evidence of damage. At 5J there was a slight flattening of the rod at the point of impact. At 10J the denting was more pronounced and a region of longitudinal cracking and fibre damage was seen in the region of impact. In addition the sample was effectively split into two by a single longitudinal crack running the length of the specimen, see fig 5. At 40J there was no great increase in the depth of the dent but multiple longitudinal cracking was seen remote from the point of impact.

Fig 4. End fittings for compression testing

Fig 5. Cross-section through unprotected rod impacted with 10J (redrawn from micrograph for clarity)

The overwound rods were impacted at 10 & 40J, then the overwind was removed and the samples examined. At 10J no denting or cracking could be seen, the only evidence that the sample had been impacted was two scuff marks on the surface, attributed to movement of the tight aramid overwind under the influence of the indenter. At 40J no denting or longitudinal cracking could be seen and a slightly larger area of scuffing was detected. In this case some damage was seen, as two partial compression creases on the upper surface of the rod, see fig 6. These creases were attributed to the global bending produced by the impact event rather than directly to an interaction between the indenter and the rod. It should be noted that clear dents were apparent in the aramid overwind at both 10 & 40J.

The standard energy levels for impacting specimens to be compression tested were set at 0, 10 & 40J for both unprotected and protected specimens.

Fig 6. Appearance of damage in clamped rod impacted at 40J

COMPRESSION TESTING

Unimpacted

The unwound rods failed at a mean stress of 950MPa (Vf in all cases normalised to 60%). Failure initiated at the end fitting.

The wound rods failed at a mean stress of 1190MPa. Failure was by kink banding remote from the end fittings.

The failure of the unwound rods was probably initiated at the stress concentration associated with the sudden transition from the very stiff end fitting to the radially much more compliant test piece. The suppression of this failure mode by the overwind was not predicted but is understandable as the overwind greatly increases the effective radial stiffness and reduces the effective Poisson’s ratio of the composite rod elements.

Post impact

The compressive strength of impacted specimens is shown in table 1 below. Winding patterns and impact conditions are expressed in the format: number of layers / tension in tow (kg) / impact energy (J). Testing was carried out under displacement control.

Table 1. Results of compression testing on protected and unprotected rods

	0/0/10	0/0/40	7/16/ 10	7/16/ 40	7/8.2/ 40	7/1.7/ 40	3/16/ 40	3/1.7/ 40
Failure stress MPa	592	304	1098	960	768	638	656	488
% unimpacted unprotected	62	32	116	101	81	67	69	51
% unimpacted protected	50	26	92	81	65	54	55	41
Performance ratio*	NA	1	NA	2.2	1.76	1.46	1.83	1.36

* Performance ratio is defined as the ratio of compressive strengths for protected and unprotected specimens impacted at 40J, taking into account the additional weight of aramid overwind

With the standard 7/16 overwind the post impact compressive strength of the protected specimens is greater than that of unimpacted, unprotected specimens. Even for the very lightest overwinds there is a substantial improvement in the post impact compression strength compared to unprotected specimens that have been impacted at the same energy level. Another observation during the compressive testing of the standard overwind specimens was that even when the load on the specimen dropped as a result of kink band formation failure was not catastrophic. Continued loading resulted in further kink band formation, fig 7 shows a failed specimen exhibiting 8 separate kink bands. The specimen shown in fig 7 was still carrying more than 80% of the peak load when the test was terminated.

Fig7. Multiple kink bands can be propagated without collapse for overwound specimens

The failure modes for the impacted specimens were as noted below (same specimen identification notation as in table 1).

0/0/10. Brooming failure from the region of the dent caused by the impact

0/0/40. Specimen barrelled as the sections of rod, separated by longitudinal splits, buckled

7/16/0. Kink banding remote from the end fitting

7/16/10. Kink banding initiating at the end fitting. It is not possible to say whether the impact caused any damage at the end-fitting region prior to test.

7/16/40. Small compression creases would be expected due to impact. Multiple kink band formation on compressive loading. See fig 7.

7/8.2/40. Two partial kink bands formed during the impact. A very wide kink band was formed under compression loading between these two partial kink bands.

7/1.7/40. Longitudinal splitting could be seen in this specimen, together with four partial kink bands caused by the impact. A wide kink band was formed under compression loading between two of the partial kink bands.

3/16/40. No longitudinal splitting, two partial kink bands. A wide kink band was formed under compression loading between these two partial kink bands.

3/1.7/40. Multiple longitudinal splitting with complex partial kink bands in the region of impact. Kink bands propagate from the partial kink bands under compressive load. Kink bands are not continuous across the longitudinal splitting.

It should be noted that, although the partial kink bands induced by impact are clearly associated with the failure process under compressive load the compressive failure does not occur by simple propagation of these partial bands.

Fig 8 shows a sketch of the features seen in a cross section through sample 3/16/40.

Fig 8. Complex failure surfaces in sample 3/16/40

DISCUSSION

The aramid fibre overwind can be seen to be performing three distinct functions, each of which is making a contribution to the protective effect that is seen in the compression after impact data. Firstly the overwind can absorb impact energy to lessen the peak load experienced by the composite rod. Secondly the overwind changes the internal stress state in the rod during the impact event, reducing the severity of damage. Thirdly the overwind changes the internal stress state in the compression testing changing the response of the rod to compressive loads. These functions are considered in more detail below.

The tension in the wrapping fibres induces a radial compression in the unidirectionally aligned fibre reinforced composite rod. When such an overwrapped rod is impacted, several protective and energy absorbing mechanisms can come into play, substantially reducing the loads experienced by the rod.

These mechanisms include:

1. Displacement of high strength textile fibre along the rods under the influence of the impactor. This displacement will absorb some energy. That this occurs can be seen from the scuff marks exhibited post-impact on the rod surface.
2. Crushing of high strength textile fibre under the impactor. This crushing will absorb a lot of energy.

Mechanisms 1 & 2 absorb energy and reduce the deceleration rate of the impactor and hence reduce the peak load.

In addition the high strength textile fibre layer increases the effective radius of curvature of the impactor which decreases the peak contact stress in the rod for a given peak load.

The three mechanisms enumerated above will reduce the peak stresses generated in the impacted rod by contact with the impacting object. If the high strength fibre was wound under little or no tension these mechanisms would still be effective, although the first mechanism would be expected to be less effective.

The tensioned winding induces a radial compression in the composite element. Splitting due to the transverse stresses induced by the impact loads can only occur when the stresses are equal to the radial compression stress plus the unmodified transverse strength of the composite element. In addition the radial compression will enhance the shear strength of the composite element. With improvements to the winding rig it should be possible to induce radial compressive stresses of the same magnitude as the unmodified transverse strength. Thus a great increase in the applied peak transverse tensile stress will be needed to initiate splitting failure.

This last mechanism, in concert with the first three mechanisms results in very much higher impact energies being required to initiate a damage state in the overwound unidirectionally aligned fibre reinforced composite rod element than would be the case for unprotected elements.

An unprotected element relies on the toughness of its constituent materials to resist the propagation of damage after this damage has been initiated. The tensioned overwinding provides a resistance to an increase in effective volume of the composite element (such as would be caused by flattening, ovalisation, cracking, splitting or delamination) which is completely lacking in the unprotected element. This mechanism effectively increases the toughness of the composite element to resist damage propagation. Thus even if the mechanisms protecting against the initiation of damage are overcome by a very high impact force the use of a tensioned overwind will still minimise the size of the damage zone caused by the impact event.

When an unprotected composite element of circular cross section is subjected to an impact event sufficient to split it into two equally sized semi-circular cross sections the stability of that element under axial compression loads is very greatly reduced; even assuming that no damage is done beyond the simple splitting. The element's ability to resist compression loads is more than halved by the impact. In the case of an overwound element, the two semi-circles are forced into intimate contact by the radial pressure exerted by the tensioned overwind so that the two semi-circles act as a single unit and retain a high stability under axial compressive loads. Thus even if the mechanisms protecting against the initiation and propagation of damage are overcome by a very high impact force the use of a tensioned overwind will still minimise the effect of that impact on the critical mechanical property of compressive stability.

We do not currently have a large enough database of different tensions, numbers of layers, impact energies and support conditions to be able to unambiguously assign which of the mechanisms enumerated above are most important in providing the improvements in performance. However, a comparison of the 7/1.7/40 and 7/16/40 results indicates that, as expected, the level of pre-stress generated does play a major role. For these two specimens the amount of aramid fibre present was identical, the only difference being in applied tension, the sample using the higher tension gave a dramatically better performance in terms of suppressing impact induced damage and maximising post-impact strength.

Other routes to protective schemes include solutions such as rubber or foam surfaces on the fibre reinforced composite elements. These can be successful in permitting the elements to tolerate a greater level of impact before damage is done, but have no influence on either the propagation of such damages once initiated or on the residual strength of impacted and damaged elements. In addition the traditional solutions may either give poor space efficiency if based on foams, or lead to a large increase in weight if based on rubber layers. Finally, the foam surface in foam based protections is easily damaged, which can lead to an unnecessarily conservative element replacement regime; on the other hand the rubber based protections may not give an external indication that an impact event has taken place, leading to damaged elements remaining in service

CONCLUSIONS

It has been conclusively demonstrated that imposing a radial compressive prestress on a unidirectional CFRP rod very greatly enhances the rod's resistance to damage arising from

impact with a rigid indenter. Even when damage is initiated by impact, the residual compressive strength is increased by the constraint of the overwind, and multiple kink bands can be generated, rather than the first kink band being catastrophic. The level of prestress imposed by the overwind is seen to be the most important single factor in the protection awarded by the overwind, although other energy absorbing mechanisms are also contributing to the overall effect. For the heaviest overwind reported here the compressive strength after a 40J impact was more than twice that of an unprotected specimen even when taking into account the additional weight of the aramid overwind. In addition to the high level of protection awarded by the overwind, the layer of aramid fibres is substantially and permanently dented by the impact. The overwound rods exhibit the opposite behaviour to most composites in that they show impact damage without suffering deleterious effects, whilst most composites can suffer severe reductions in strength from barely-visible impact damage. The analysis that has been done to date indicates that, although sensitive to the exact lay-up and geometry, high levels of prestress can be imposed on tubular components, suggesting that this protective approach would be of great practical value in, for example, high pressure tubing and similar applications. Work to date has utilised tensions in the aramid fibres that have been limited by the available winding equipment rather than the creep and static fatigue properties of aramid fibres. Improved winding equipment will permit the optimisation of the overwinding approach to protecting rod and tubular elements.

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